

HΣPHÆSTUS

Heritage in EuroPe: new tecHnologies in crAft for prEServing and innovaTing
fUtureS

Project No. 101095123

Deliverable 4.2

A new life-long learning methodology for craft-makers

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Abstract	A methodology to provide necessary training and micro-credentialing in skills and key competences for the facilitation of craft making as a vehicle for social cohesion and personal and professional fulfilment, including: digital and technology- based competences, interpersonal and intergenerational learning skills on active citizenship, entrepreneurship, cultural awareness and expression, gender gap awareness in craft ecosystems and how to address it.
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Scheduled updates

The Report is a document which evolves during the lifespan of the project and registers all relevant changes in the life cycle of the HEPHAESTUS project. This document will be updated with more information about the Visual Identity and the communication and dissemination plan and strategy.

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About HEPHAESTUS

Working across the **regional craft ecosystems** of **Bassano del Grappa (IT)**, **Bornholm (DK)**, **Dals Långed (SE)**, and **Venice (IT)**, the overarching ambition of HEPHAESTUS is *to bring together cutting-edge technologies with traditional craft to co-create solutions in the form of a suite of tools, methodologies, and business models to make the future of European craft ecosystems socially, culturally, environmentally, and economically sustainable*. HEPHAESTUS will **test and evaluate solutions** co-created across the four regional craft ecosystems within a “**Future of Craft**” **Green Living Lab** situated in Bornholm, a Danish Island and regional municipality given the title of World Craft Region. Ultimately, the project sets out to create a **sustainable network** (especially including regional realities) of heritage sites, cultural and creative sectors, institutions, universities, local, regional and national authorities, enterprises, and other relevant stakeholders engaged in preservation of craft heritage that will take the project’s results, further adapt and deploy them in a broader range of craft ecosystems, and ensure a long- lasting legacy of the HEPHAESTUS project. The work of HEPHAESTUS is organized around six work packages, each responsible for one specific objective related to the overarching ambition, namely:

Objective 1: Develop new **sustainable business models** for the craft sectors.

Objective 2: Combine **cutting-edge technologies** with craft materials and processes to research and develop new applications and solutions for the digitisation and innovation of the craft sector to improve sustainability and social innovation.

Objective 3: Explore visions for the role of **craft in the future**, integrating emerging technologies and contributing to the circular economy, by engaging craft communities in a participatory ideation process.

Objective 4: Develop a **lifelong learning methodology** and a set of innovative curricula to equip craft-makers with diverse skillsets for innovation.

Objective 5: Establish a **Green Living Lab** for testing the HEPHAESTUS innovations.

Objective 6: To design and operationalise a **bespoke dissemination, communication, and exploitation** strategy.

To achieve these objectives, the consortium includes prominent universities, business schools and a private organization selected for their proven knowledge and expertise on craft heritage, craft materials, and the use of digital technologies and cutting-edge

technologies in craft, the proposed innovative and original contributions as well as their trustworthiness. A unique value added brought to the consortium is represented also by the group of third parties, including craft makers and craft associations, as well as Museums and Municipality representatives, from each of the four regional ecosystems.

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is of type OTHER; however, we have prepared a document to accompany it that describes the podcast we are creating, titled **Pod-Craft: stories and skills from the world of craft-making**.

This deliverable proposes an innovative and flexible learning approach for craft-makers by integrating digital education and mentorship. The methodology ensures that craft-makers gain essential skills in technology, entrepreneurship, sustainability, and communication, enhancing their ability to navigate the evolving craft industry.

PodCraft: A Podcast-Based Learning Tool

A core element of this deliverable is the creation of **PodCraft: Stories and Skills from the World of Craft-Making**, a podcast designed to offer accessible, engaging, and modular learning experiences. Unlike traditional training programs, PodCraft aligns with the unique needs of craft-makers by allowing them to learn while working, leveraging the popularity of audio content to deliver education in an efficient and convenient format.

The podcast is structured around **two main series**:

- **Craft Tools** – Exploring digital tools, new materials, and sustainable innovations.
- **Craft Talks** – Featuring business models, success stories, and entrepreneurial insights from craft-makers.

Key **learning areas** covered in the podcast include:

- **Technical skills and innovation**: exploring advancements such as 3D printing, AI applications, and material experimentation.
- **Business and management**: Covering business models, strategies, intellectual property law, leadership, and marketing.
- **Communication and digital presence**: Addressing challenges in social media, e-commerce, and branding.
- **Sustainability & circular economy**: Showcasing best practices from Bornholm and beyond.
- **Peer mentorship for lifelong learning**: Encouraging community-driven education and knowledge exchange.

The choice of a podcast format is driven by:

1. **Flexibility** – Craft-makers can listen while working, reducing time constraints.
2. **Accessibility** – Available in multiple languages (English, Danish, Swedish, and Italian) to ensure inclusivity.
3. **Scalability** – Can be integrated into formal education systems or professional training programs.

4. **Affordability** – Free, reducing financial barriers often associated with traditional courses.

While HEPHAESTUS cannot issue micro-credentials directly as an EU-funded research project, PodCraft serves as an **open educational resource** that institutions can incorporate into their credentialing programs. Combined with other structured learning experiences, such as the project's **mentoring program** and **technology-driven methodology**, the podcast offers skill-based.

Disclaimer

This document reflects only the author's view, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Acknowledgement

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Podcast as a learning tool: *Pod-craft: stories and skills from the world of craft-making*

This deliverable is of type OTHER; however, we have prepared a document to accompany it that describes the podcast we are creating, titled **Pod-Craft: stories and skills from the world of craft-making**.

Directly related to one of the core concepts of the Hephaestus projects, namely lifelong learning (WP4, WP5), one of the objectives we set for ourselves during the project was to provide innovative learning tools to craft-makers and those interested in approaching this profession. Of course, the label “innovative” takes on very different meanings depending on whether we are dealing with “new” professions, where training and apprenticeships are yet to be discovered or institutionalized, or with more traditional professions, which certainly evolve over time and with technology but have existed long enough for skills and learning methods to be relatively widespread, and where the availability of learning tools is not lacking. This is the case for crafts. Consequently, within Hephaestus, instead of imposing top-down (or external) training solutions on craft-makers, we decided to listen to their voices and needs. Specifically, during the mapping of the perceived educational gaps for craft-makers we managed to understand which skills are perceived as more relevant for the different fields of artisanal production. Therefore, we sought to understand not only what craft-makers need to learn but also how it is important for them to learn.

Additionally, in continuity with the previous deliverable (D4.1), we focused on five macro areas of competences. Based on the interviews conducted during the project, focus groups, and various informal conversations with craft-makers during project meetings, exhibitions, and workshop visits, we reached three key conclusions that guide our proposed learning methodology:

1. **Time is the scarcest resource for craft-makers**, who are constantly striving to find a work-life balance that allows them to live off their craft without being consumed by it. Often, due to production and sales methods—as explained in greater detail in another project deliverable (D1.3 on business models)—craft-makers struggle to make a living solely from craft-making,

particularly in ecosystems where tourism is highly seasonal. Consequently, the time available for learning is very limited, and artisans prefer to dedicate it to developing technical and craftsmanship skills (see deliverable 4.1). However, when artisans are working—and they work a lot—their hands are busy, as are their eyes, but their ears are free. Many of the artisans we interviewed in their workshops were, in fact, listening to music or podcasts. When specifically asked, many respondents told us they do not necessarily need “light” content, as it does not distract them from the manual work they are doing. For this reason, we decided to develop a **podcast** that does not replicate the countless online resources already available for artisans but instead offers something additional and different. This is the rationale that guides the development of *“Pod-Craft: stories and skills from the world of craft-making”*

2. **Different topics require different approaches.** As highlighted in deliverable 4.1, for example, many artisans have a dual attitude toward the promotion, communication, and sale of their products. On one hand, communication is essential: *“If I weren’t on Instagram, I wouldn’t exist, but I don’t want to be on Instagram,”* said a craftswoman from the Venetian ecosystem, perfectly encapsulating this duality. For artisans, communication, pricing, product photography, time management, and mastery of management techniques are crucial yet underdeveloped skills. For these topics, short podcast lessons can be particularly effective in introducing craft-makers to the subjects, thereby reducing perceived learning barriers. To ensure this, we decided to involve not only the academics participating in the Hephaestus project—many of whom specialize in strategy, **management**, organizational development, business models, and more—but also other **craft-makers** who can share exemplary success stories, recognizing that peer-to-peer communication plays a fundamental role in learning. Another theme that can be extensively addressed through podcasts is **technological innovation**, or rather, literacy about what technological innovation can do for craft-makers. One of the most interesting findings from deliverable 4.1 is that many craft-makers do not consider technological skills to be particularly relevant to them. This happens notwithstanding the fact that the range of technological skills covered in the survey was quite broad, including automation and robotic production, digitization, 3D printing/modeling, AI interaction, and research/experimentation skills. We believe the lack of importance attributed to these skills stems not from a real assessment of what these competencies can offer craft-maker but rather from a lack of knowledge (again due to a lack of time) about what technological innovation can do for craftsmanship without altering its essence. For this reason, our innovative methodology on the technological front involves supplementing some podcast lessons with a specific methodology on technology-driven innovation (D2.2).

- 3. Every ecosystem—and even every craft-maker—requires tailored solutions.** After nearly two years of interviews, focus groups, visits to artisan workshops, and surveys of places of design, production, and sales, this conclusion is paramount. Even when the challenges are the same, every ecosystem demands different solutions. Zooming in further, even craft-makers facing similar problems require different solutions. For this reason, our approach will complement podcast listening with a mentoring program for craft-makers, which will be implemented by our partner UNIVE (for reference, see Task 6.5; D6.5), with participation from other consortium universities. Specifically, following the podcasts, focus groups will be organized where artisans can share their experiences, which will be used to create new podcast episodes and foster networking on specific podcast-related topics. Additionally, Ca' Foscari will organize mentoring cycles focused on materiality and artisanal practices. For each material (e.g., glass, paper, clay, wood), a craft-maker will take on the role of coach for colleagues working with different materials. Each participating artisan will both teach and learn from others. Researchers from Hephaestus will also be involved in the mentoring sessions to observe dynamics for research purposes, facilitate discussions on managerial implications, and help strengthen the connections between craftsmanship and management. This meeting format will also serve as a model for the Living Labs of Bornholm.

In addition, we can share an anecdote that gave us much to think about: during the annual meeting in Dåls Langed, at the end of the first year, some craft-makers mentioned that the meeting would have been more enjoyable and easier to follow if, instead of sitting idle and trying to focus, they could have participated in a craft workshop during the conferences to stay more engaged and more focused also on the talks. So, the idea of a podcast for craft makers originated from these needs. While working with their hands in their studios, craft makers have the possibility to listen to the podcast. Moreover, the format of the podcast is a more accessible tool for craft makers and professionals who lack time to learn the issues, tools, and best practices of craft making than having to read a hundred-page manual or report. Having the possibility to listen to a 20/30-minute episode focused on a specific matter regarding craft making techniques or an interview with an international craft maker makes these issues more accessible and programmable in terms of time, work schedule, and tone. Finally, many online or in-presence courses already exist for craft makers who want to improve their skills or learn new techniques, but often they are either too expensive or too demanding in terms of time, so they are usually not a useful solution for the majority of craft-makers. For this reason, our aim was not to create yet another course for craft makers, but rather a podcast, freely available online and translated in multiple languages, that could address the most challenging issues craft

makers face, offering possible solutions, tools, and considerations. Thus, the podcast is a complementary learning tool thought firstly for craft makers but also for scholars, professionals, and other interested people in the topic of contemporary craft making. It is part of the new life-long learning methodology for craft makers to provide necessary training and micro-credentialing in skills and key competences for the facilitation of craft making as a vehicle for social cohesion and personal and professional fulfilment, including digital and technology based competences, interpersonal and intergenerational learning skills on active citizenship, entrepreneurship, cultural awareness and expression, gender gap awareness in craft ecosystem and hot to address it. This additionally relates to Task 2.2, which focuses on designing an innovative craft-driven innovation methodology for integrating the use of cutting-edge technologies. As shown in Figure 1, a podcast episode about digital tools for production and design processes is planned for February 2025, in collaboration with FabLab Venice.

Editorial calendar

The podcast is titled “*PodCraft: stories and skills from the world of craft making*” and it delves into the life of craft makers, why people choose a craft life, and what it really takes to be a great artisan.

The podcast has two series: *Craft Tools* and *Craft Talks*, the first investigates the tools of craft making including new cutting-edge technologies, communication, and workplaces; while *Craft Talks* explores in-depth the business model and entrepreneurial experiences of craft makers in the three ecosystems, analyzing the challenges and the innovative aspects of their practices in how to make a living out of craft.

Also, Pod-craft's episodes will explore seven main themes, each designed to address key areas of interest for craft-makers while providing a diverse and engaging learning experience.

One of the central focuses will be on **craft-making skills and technical expertise**, delving into the practical and artistic dimensions of craftsmanship. A planned episode titled *Arts for Craft: D20* will examine the value of art-based research in enhancing craft-making practices. Additionally, several episodes will feature firsthand accounts from artisans sharing the outcomes of their experimental

work. For instance, stories might include Elena Rausse or Valentina Stocco experimenting with unique clays sourced from the Brenta River or the Venetian Lagoon, offering listeners valuable insights into the creative process.

The second theme centers on **technological skills**, showcasing how innovative tools and methods can transform craftsmanship. Topics will range from Alberta Menegaldo's insights into 3D printing and digitization at FabLab to Christina Schou Christensen's exploration of micro-crushing techniques for glass and ceramics. We also would like to have Jokum Jensen contribute by discussing machinery designed to complement traditional tools like hammers, emphasizing sustainability. Episodes on AI interaction will explore how artificial intelligence can complement and enhance craft practices, offering new perspectives on technological integration.

Another significant theme is **business skills**, approached through a series of academic talks. These episodes will cover a wide range of topics, such as intellectual property law for artisans, presented by Vishv Priya Kohli, and an analysis of the resurgence of craft in modern economies by Marta Gasparin. Discussions on leadership, business models, and authenticity, led by speakers like Elena Raviola, Fabrizio Panozzo, or Maria Lusiani will provide craft-makers with essential tools to navigate their professional landscape. Sessions with Luca Pareschi and Francesca Leonardi will focus on training methodologies, while other episodes will explore the interplay between craft and tourism, the importance of districts, and project management skills. Sustainability will also be a recurring topic, with David Christensen providing insights into sustainable practices tailored to artisans.

Effective **communication** is another pillar of the podcast, as many craft-makers struggle to showcase their work in the digital age. Episodes on this theme will explore strategies for building websites, managing social media accounts like Instagram, and leveraging e-commerce platforms. Margot Bustamante will share her research on digital communication, and we are planning to have Valentina Stocco discussing her dual role as a ceramist and photographer, offering practical advice on presenting craft online. Other episodes will tackle marketing, promotion, and pricing, providing craft-makers with actionable insights to elevate their brand and business.

An essential part of the podcast will focus on **making a living from craft**, sharing real-life stories and strategies from artisans who have successfully turned their passion into a sustainable livelihood. Voices like Cosima Montavoci will provide valuable perspectives, alongside stories from artisans based in Bornholm and Dals Långed/Fengersfors, offering listeners a glimpse into diverse ecosystems and challenges.

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The podcast will also delve into the **business models that define different craft ecosystems**, exploring how these systems shape the craft landscape. Episodes will highlight examples such as Nove, an industrial district studied by Ca' Foscari and Tor Vergata, and the balance between craft and tourism in Venice. Other episodes will discuss the craft-maker community in Not Quite, as well as the relationship between craft and circular economy on Bornholm, including collaborations with BOFA.

Finally, the podcast will reflect on **sister projects and lifelong learning**, drawing attention to tools and methodologies developed in other initiatives. These episodes may include insights from the CRAEFT project and its video tutorials on various techniques, showcasing how collaborative learning and innovative tools can enhance craft-making practices and foster continuous development.

Together, these themes weave a comprehensive narrative, blending technical skills, practical advice, personal stories, and academic insights to create an enriching resource for craft-makers and enthusiasts alike.

The recording of the episodes is divided into three periods, according to the availability of craft makers and scholars taking part in it and to the calendar of the project, limiting as much as possible the carbon footprint of the participants:

- By the end of January 2025: delivery of the first pilot episode;
- By the end of September 2025: delivery of the second wave of episodes additional episodes (12);
- By the end of December 2025: delivery of the third wave of episodes (for a total of at least 24).

Each episode will be recorded and edited by the Hephaestus team and will be disseminated on the major streaming platforms and on the project website <https://hephaestuscraft.eu/>.

A very important aspect concerns the language. We certainly cannot expect all artisans to be able to listen to podcasts solely in English, especially while working on their daily activities. Consequently, the episodes will be translated into English and the three languages of the ecosystems (Danish, Swedish, and Italian), with potential support from AI and automatic translation tools to ensure maximum accessibility for all craft-makers and listeners.

We have ruled out the idea of subtitling the podcasts, as this would make it impossible to simply listen to them, and we instead prefer to produce the same episodes in multiple languages. Whenever possible, episodes will be recorded directly in multiple languages (e.g., if the guest is Italian and speaks English). Alternatively, we will use AI tools to transcribe the interview text. The interview will then be re-recorded by people fluent in the chosen language for that recording, or we may utilize AI voice simulators, but only if this does not compromise the quality of the podcast.

All participants in the podcast will be required to sign a release form in compliance with GDPR regulations.

Below is a tentative list of upcoming episodes. We will also produce several episodes that will allow us to explore the seven areas described earlier. These episodes will be produced after the initial ones.

Figure 1: Tentative editorial plan

The order of the list does not reflect the order of publication.

Figure 1

	When and where	Podcast speakers	Tentative Topic
1	January 2025 CBS Copenhagen	Marta Gasparin with Andrea Beye/Lea Jacobsen	<i>Pilot episode</i> : craft resurgence and introduction to the Hephaestus project
2	January 2025 CBS Copenhagen	Priya Kohli with Marta Gasparin/Lea Jacobsen	<i>Craft tools</i> : IP law in craft making, legal tools to protect craft creations
3	February 2025 Venice and Bassano	Linnea Dalstrand (craftmaker from Däls Langed) with Luca Pareschi/Francesca Leonardi	<i>Craft talks</i> : How to make a living from craft? Innovation and cutting-hedge technologies (FabLab residency)
4	February 2025 Venice and Bassano	Lukas Arons (craftmaker from Däls Langed) with Luca Pareschi/Francesca Leonardi	<i>Craft talks</i> : How to make a living from craft? Commercializing craft through galleries

5	February 2025 Venice and Bassano	Jokum Jensen (craftmaker from Däls Langed) with Luca Pareschi/Francesca Leonardi	<i>Craft talks:</i> How to make a living from craft? Craft practices and peer network
6	February 2025 Venice and Bassano	Elena Rausse (craftmaker from Bassano/Nove) with Luca Pareschi/Francesca Leonardi	<i>Craft talks:</i> How to make a living from craft? Relationship with craft and heritage
7	February 2025 Venice and Bassano	Bianca Bonaldi (craftmaker from Bassano/Nove) with Luca Pareschi/Francesca Leonardi	<i>Craft talks:</i> How to make a living from craft?
8	February 2025 Venice and Bassano	Pol Polloniato (craftmaker from Bassano/Nove) with Luca Pareschi/Francesca Leonardi	<i>Craft talks:</i> How to make a living from craft? relationship with craft and the territory in the ecosystem of Nove and Bassano.
9	February 2025 Venice and Bassano	Alberta Menegaldo (FabLab) with Luca Pareschi/Francesca Leonardi	<i>Craft tools:</i> Digital tools for production and design processes (3d printing)
10	February 2025 Venice and Bassano	Bottega Nove with Luca Pareschi/Francesca Leonardi	<i>Craft talks:</i> How to make a living from craft? The example of a craft company
11	February 2025 Venice and Bassano	Alberta Menegaldo (FabLab) with Luca Pareschi/Francesca Leonardi	<i>Craft tools:</i> AI and craft
12	June 2025 Bornholm	Elena Raviola Luca Pareschi/Francesca Leonardi	<i>Craft tools:</i> Leadership toward organization of professional work
13	June 2025 Bornholm	Marta Gasparin/Marius Gudmand and Helena Hansson/Karl Hallberg	<i>Craft tools:</i> Craft business models in the different ecosystems

		with Luca Pareschi/Francesca Leonardi	
14	June 2025 Bornholm	Christina Schou Christensen (craft maker in Bornholm) and Margot Bustamante, with Luca Pareschi/Francesca Leonardi	<i>Craft talks:</i> Innovation and entrepreneurship in craft making
15	June 2025 Bornholm	BOFA (David Andreas Mana-Ay Christensen and Dorthe Møller Paulsen) with Luca Pareschi/Francesca Leonardi	<i>Craft talks:</i> Sustainability and circular economy in Bornholm
16	June 2025 Bornholm	Lova Öberg (craftmaker from Däls Langed) with Luca Pareschi/Francesca Leonardi	<i>Craft talks:</i> How to make a living from craft? Gender and woodworking
17	June 2025 Bornholm	Sara Jeffries (craftmaker from Bornholm) with Luca Pareschi/Francesca Leonardi	<i>Craft talks:</i> How to make a living from craft?
18	June 2025 Bornholm	Roberto Beltrami (craftmaker from Venice) with Luca Pareschi/Francesca Leonardi	<i>Craft talks:</i> How to make a living from craft?
19	September 2025 – November 2025 (TBD)	Camilla Ferri and Maria Lusiani with Luca Pareschi/Francesca Leonardi	<i>Craft talks:</i> Authenticity in craft practices
20	September 2025 – November 2025 (TBD)	Manfredi De Bernard and Fabrizio Panozzo with Luca Pareschi/Francesca Leonardi	<i>Craft talks:</i> Business model in different ecosystems. The role of the craft districts in Nove
21	September 2025 – November 2025 (TBD)	D20 – Sergio Marchesini and Raffaella Rivi (D20) with Luca Pareschi/Francesca Leonardi	<i>Craft talks:</i> what is the use of art-based research for craft?

22	September 2025 – November 2025 (TBD)	Elena Raviola with Luca Pareschi/Francesca Leonardi	<i>Craft talks</i> : Business model in different ecosystems. The craft makers community in Not Quite
23	September 2025 – November 2025 CBS Copenhagen	Rasmus Johnsen with Andrea Beye	<i>Craft tools</i> : Lifelong learning methodologies

Showcase Example:

Pilot Episode, 24/01/2025 with Marta Gasparin: craft resurgence and introduction to the Hephaestus project

On January 24, 2025, we recorded the first episode of *PodCraft* at Copenhagen Business School. This episode introduces listeners to craftsmanship, the cultural and creative industries, and the contemporary resurgence of craft. Through this discussion, *Hephaestus* is framed within the broader context of preserving craft practices and exploring how craft provides a space for reflection—offering alternative ways of organizing in contrast to today’s industrialized, fast-paced, and capitalist structures.

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For craft makers, this conversation is particularly relevant. Not only does this episode serve as an introduction to the podcast while ‘setting the scene’, it also helps them better understand the academic, social, and cultural significance of their work, which can support them in sustaining their practices. By grasping the broader context, they can refine their storytelling and communication strategies to navigate challenges more effectively.

The episode also introduces the *Hephaestus* project, addressing key challenges faced by craft makers in Europe, and examining whether certain places or communities are more conducive to craft-based work. Additionally, it explores sustainable business models in the craft sector, highlighting the need for innovation and development in this field.

For further details, please refer to the script below.

Script

1. [A quote of a particularly meaningful phrase from the interview. Decontextualized, without the question, but it immediately throws us into the heart of things.]

2. [Intro of podcraft, same for all episodes]

[prerecorded] We hear about craft-making more and more often: from stories of people rediscovering meaning through manual work, to the pride of creating with your own hands. From tales of work organized differently from capitalism, to EU-funded initiatives supporting the craft sector. But what exactly do we talk about when we talk about craft?

“Pod-Craft: stories and skills from the world of craft-making” is here to explore that question. We’ll dive into the lives and tools of craft-makers, and we’ll uncover why people choose the craft life - and what it really takes to be a great artisan.

Brought to you by the Hephaestus Project, Pod-Craft is your backstage pass to the world of making—so tune in and let’s get our hands dirty!

3. [jingle]

4. [20 seconds Introduction of today's guest, different for each episode but following the same structure, saying one relevant thing about the guest.]

[Read by the interviewer:] Marta Gasparin is the principal investigator of the Hephaestus project, which researches craft with the aim of innovating it, while also enhancing and preserving it. Marta, an associate professor at Copenhagen Business School, will talk to us today about the resurgence of craft.

5. Body of the interview

1. I'm Andrea Beye from CBS. Good morning, Marta, and thank you for being here. Let's start with the basics. The first thing I'd like to ask is: what's the point of studying craft? Aren't there other sectors that contribute much more to economic well-being?

2. But what can craft tell us about our world? And what can studying craft do for our society?

3. And what about craft-makers? What are the main challenges that craft-makers face today in Europe?

4. Is it the same everywhere in Europe, or are there places or communities that are better suited for craft-makers?

5. Marta, you're the principal investigator of Hephaestus, a project about craft. But what exactly is the Hephaestus project?

6. I know that in Hephaestus, you'll also focus on craft business models. Why is that relevant? [This can be substituted with any other Hephaestus topic, such as sustainability.]

7. Marta, one last question—we're asking this to everyone: tools are essential for craft-makers. But what's your favourite tool in your work?

6. [Conclusion, the same for all episodes, prerecorded]: *Pod-Craft is a podcast produced by the Hephaestus Craft project, funded by the European Commission under Grant Agreement ID: 101095123, as part of the work package dedicated to training and lifelong learning. Pod-Craft features interviews and conversations with craft-makers, academics, and artists, exploring the essence of*

craftsmanship and offering training for practitioners and aspiring craft-makers. Pod-Craft is available for free on Spotify and at hephaestuscraft.eu

Toward a life-long learning methodology

The podcast series is a fundamental part, together with the craft-technology driven innovative methodology (Deliverable 2.2) and the mentoring program (Deliverable 6.5), towards an establishment of Life-long Learning approach, which are planned as deliverables in the next months. As previously described, the podcast offers a series of specific contents related to craft making, tools, and the understanding of craft which can form self-standing learning experiences. As podcasts are already tools for knowledge in formal and credited university courses, PodCraft can surely be learning pills focused on specific topics, on craft-making skills and technical expertise, technological skills, business skills, communication, and different business models.

The European approach to micro-credentials aims at providing a clear definition and European standards to allow for the learning outcomes of small learning experiences to be easily recognized and understood. As defined by the European Commission (2022), a micro-credential is the “record of the learning outcomes that a learner has acquired following a small volume of learning” (p.10). These courses and learning experiences are designed to provide the learner with specific knowledge, skills and competences that respond to societal, personal, cultural or labour market needs.

Micro-credentials are small units of learning that certify specific skills, knowledge, or competences acquired through short educational experiences. They are designed to complement traditional qualifications rather than replace them, offering a flexible and modular approach to lifelong learning. In the European Union, micro-credentials follow common standards for quality assurance, transparency, and recognition, making them comparable and portable across institutions and countries. The importance of micro-credentials lies in

D4.2. A new life-long learning methodology for craft-makers

their ability to address the fast-changing demands of society and the labor market. They also support lifelong learning by making education more accessible to a diverse range of learners, including those in non-traditional education pathways. By establishing a European framework, the EU aims to enhance trust, recognition, and portability of these credentials across member states, ensuring that they contribute to employability and personal development.

That said, not all institutions can issue micro-credentials. To offer micro-credentials, institutions must define clear learning outcomes, assess them through reliable methods, and apply internal and external quality assurance aligned with European standards. Micro-credentials must include standardized information such as the awarding body, workload (in ECTS where possible), qualification level, and assessment methods to facilitate recognition across institutions and countries. They should also be designed for easy integration into broader educational and professional frameworks. Additionally, institutions are encouraged to issue micro-credentials in digital formats through secure platforms like Europass, allowing learners to store, share, and verify their achievements (European Commission, 2022).

As a result, we, as a Horizon Europe project, cannot issue micro-credentials. As a Horizon Europe project, we operate within a research and innovation funding framework that does not include the authority to issue formal educational credentials, including micro-credentials. The accreditation and certification of learning require institutional quality assurance, regulatory compliance, and integration with national and European qualification frameworks—elements that fall within the domain of higher education institutions and vocational training providers.

We have therefore chosen an alternative approach through the podcast. On one hand, the free availability of the episodes, which can be easily accessed through widely used apps, allows those who want to learn but are not interested in obtaining a credential—a common scenario among craft-makers—to listen to what interests them without any additional concerns. On the other hand, the podcast can also serve as a resource for those who wish to integrate it into their own training activities. Essentially, through the podcast, we are providing educational material that can serve as input for those who develop more formalized courses issuing micro-credentials.

Ultimately, our project contributes to the development of micro-credentials by providing open-access educational resources, such as this podcast series. These resources are designed to support skill development and knowledge-sharing in a way that complements institutional micro-credential programs. By making high-quality content freely available, we empower educational institutions and training providers to integrate our materials into their micro-credential offerings, ensuring learners have access to relevant and up-to-date knowledge. This aligns with the EU's broader goals of fostering lifelong learning, supporting digital education, and promoting the recognition of diverse learning pathways.

The podcast can easily fit into the European learning system based on micro-credentials, if paired with other forms of learning, such as the Innovative Methodology and the mentoring program, and with assessment moments integrated in a life-long learning methodology or in university or professional courses. Moreover, they can adapt to different audiences, from craft-makers who want to integrate their knowledge on specific issues, to scholars and students who want to approach craft studies from a more professional and hands-on perspective.

References

- **European Commission.** (2022). *European approach to micro-credentials in higher education: Consultation group output final report*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://education.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/document-library-docs/european-approach-micro-credentials-higher-education-consultation-group-output-final-report.pdf>

